

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Partial purification and antidiabetic effect of bioactive compounds isolated from medicinal plants

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ABSTRACT

Antidiabetic studies were conducted in human whole blood using different medicinal plant products (*Trigonella foenum graecum*, seeds; *Syzygium cumini*, seeds; *Salavadora persica*, leaves and *Terminalia chebula*, seeds). The objective of our study is to screen fractions of these four different medicinal plant products on diabetic human whole blood samples. For these studies, our group evaluated secondary metabolites through thin layer chromatography (TLC) and also determined its activity on diabetic human whole blood samples in order to determine total cellular content, free hemoglobin in the supernatant and also estimated its glucose content. The results of these studies claimed that all these fractions isolated from these medicinal plant products showed antidiabetic effect at lower doses because of decline in total cellular content, free hemoglobin in the supernatant and glucose content but maximum effect observed in case of fraction isolated from *Syzygium cumini* and *Salavadora persica*. Overall, this study claimed that all these plant fractions showed anti-diabetic activity.

Keywords: *Trigonella foenum graecum*; *Syzygium cumini*; *Salavadora persica*; *Terminalia chebula*; Antidiabetic.

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INTRODUCTION

Hyperglycemia, a biochemical hallmark in the development of diabetes, assessed by glycated hemoglobin A1c or A1C levels to reduce the long term diabetes-related complications [1, 2]. In contrast undiagnosed or untreated hyperglycemia, leads to adverse consequences and have a longer length of stay. Mostly A1C therapy is advised when blood glucose level

persistent within the range of >140-180 mg/dl as the blood glucose level >140 mg/dl is (7.8 mmol/L) considered as a hyperglycemia [3]. According to WHO report 2011, the cutoff value of HbA1c for diagnosis of diabetes is 6.5% (48 mmol/mol), while American Diabetes Association (ADA) advised the range 5.7-6.4% as a high risk range indicating the presence of intermediate hyperglycaemia [4]. Diagnosis using is more precise than that of FPG (fasting plasma glucose) and 2-h

OGTT (oral glucose tolerance test) diagnosis [5]. Available oral hypoglycemic agents such as biguanides and sulfonylurea have not yet gained much success in maintaining the proper glycemic condition maybe because of their side effects. Therefore, efforts are continuing with the development of oral antidiabetic agents without or less side effects [6]. Herbal drugs are preferred as alternative drug therapies for the conventional diabetic drugs as they are cost effective, tolerated by the patients, safer to use, etc. [7].

Medicinal plants have been used for centuries for the management and alleviation of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) and its complications. Much of the available literature in DM revealed that 1,200 medicinal plants with hypoglycemic activity [8]. Though the mechanism of these plants is not well documented, the majority of studies is being conducted to uncover the mechanism of action of these plants and their isolates. Hence, more attention is being paid to study the proper mechanism of these plant's actions along with their bioactive compounds responsible for these activities. *Galega officinalis* L. (Fabaceae) was the first medicinal plants described for its antidiabetic property [9]. In the present study, we have evaluated four plants *in vitro*, viz. *Fenugreek*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Salvadora persica* and *Terminalia chebula* for their antidiabetic activity on diabetic blood samples. All these plants are well documented for their pharmacological and medicinal properties, for example, aqueous extract of fenugreek when administered orally to the Male Wistar rats of 150 g in weight, shown improved carbendazim induced testicular toxicity and thereby attributed to the antioxidant property [10]. Tannins and flavonoids, two bioactive compound identified in *Syzygium cumini* leaves aqueous extract, have shown anti-allergic and anti-edematogenic effect in Swiss mice. *Syzygium cumini* exerts these effects by inhibiting mast cell degranulation and histamine and serotonin effects on the cells [11]. Hydroalcoholic extract of *Syzygium cumini* leaves has also shown an effective reduction in blood pressure and heart rate of spontaneously hypertensive Wistar rats by inhibiting arterial tone and extracellular calcium influx [12]. Tabatabaei and co-workers have reported the time-dependent cell proliferative effect of aqueous extract of *Salvadora persica* on human dental pulp stem cells (hDPSCs) [13]. Ethanol extract of *S. persica* is found to be effective in removing the smear layer from the coronal third of the canal wall [14]. In spite of acting as a good anticaries agent [15], *Terminalia chebula* also showed anti-arthritis effect in six-week-old male DBA/1 mice by suppressing the expression of inflammatory mediators and preventing cartilage destruction and bone erosion. The bioactive compound chebulanin, isolated from fruit part is responsible to inhibit for the anti-

arthritic collagen induced arthritis in DBA/1 mice [16]. The present study which described about antidiabetic potential of these fractions isolated from these medicinal plants i.e. *Trigonella foenum graecum*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Salvadora persica* and *Terminalia chebula*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

Seeds of fenugreek and *T. chebula* were purchased and *S. cumini* seeds and *S. persica* leaves were collected from local region of Ahmednagar (MS), India. All these plant material were authenticated by the Department of Botany, Padmashri Vikhe Patil College, Pravaranagar (Loni), Tal. Rahata, District Ahmednagar, (MS), India.

Preparation of extracts

All plant samples (*Trigonella foenum graecum* seeds, *Syzygium cumini* seeds, *Salvadora persica* leaves and *Terminalia chebula* seeds) were ground into a fine powdered form and these samples were mixed with organic solvents i.e. chloroform for fenugreek, ethanol for *S. cumini*, water for *S. persica* and petroleum ether for *T. chebula*. All chemicals were purchased from Himedia. All the extracts were transferred to orbital shaker for 3 days at room temperature. The mixture was then filtered through Whatman No. 41 filter paper. All filtrate except aqueous extract, were concentrated using rotary evaporator. Filtered aqueous extracts of *Salvadora persica*, was frozen at -77°C and finally lyophilized at -46°C [17].

Thin Layer Chromatography

Thin Layer chromatography plates were prepared by applying 0.5 mm thick coat of silica gel (with distilled water in 1:2 ratio) on a microscope. Plates were activated at 110°C for 1h before use. 10 μl sample were applied to the plates and developed in chromatographic chamber with mobile phase appropriate to the extract as shown in Table 1. Plates were dried and spots were visualized with iodine chamber. Visualized spots were retrieved using an appropriate solvent [18].

Partial identification of nature related to bioactive compounds

Partial identification of nature of bioactive compounds isolated from all four plant extracts was carried out by using different chromogens giving colour reactions specific for alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins and tannins was added to extract and specific color pattern was

observed. For alkaloids, dragendorff's reagent was used and orange coloured demonstrated positive for alkaloids. For flavonoids, magnesium ribbon and concentrated hydrochloric acid were added and formation of red pink color was observed. For saponins, Anisaldehyde sulphuric acid reagent was added which gives pinkish violet color as an indication of a positive result. Screening for tannin was carried out by adding alcoholic FeCl_3 . The greenish gray coloration confirmed the presence of tannins [19, 20].

Estimation of total cellular content and free hemoglobin content

Lysed diabetic human whole blood samples ($n = 5$; 100 μl cells containing 10^5 cells/well) were collected (Mangal pathology lab, Baramati) and cultured in 24 well flat bottom tissue culture plate for 48 h incubation along with variable doses of these fractions isolated from *Trigonella foenum graecum* (fenugreek), *Syzygium cumini*, *Salavadora persica* and *Terminalia chebula*. In this study, huminsulin 50/50 used as standard and performed all these studies in two different set of experiments. In first set, centrifuge the samples at 15000 rpm after 48 h incubation and then collect the supernatant in order to determine the total cellular or protein content [21] using NanoDrop 1000 A280 module. In NanoDrop, Beer Lambert equation ($A = E * b * c$) is applied and used for all protein calculations to correlate absorbance with concentration. In second set of experiment, lysed diabetic human whole blood samples were treated with test material and incubate for 48 h and then washed with PBS pertaining to observe the free hemoglobin in the supernatant. Finally samples were analyzed through UV visible spectrophotometer at 570 nm [21].

Estimation of glucose content

Non infected lysed human whole blood samples were cultured for 48 h incubation along with variable doses of glucose content. After incubation, centrifuge the samples

at 2500 rpm and estimate free glucose content in the supernatant. All these readings were determined and prepared standard curve pertaining to determine the glucose content in human diabetic blood samples which is determined through Nanodrop method.

Statistical analysis

The difference between control and treated group of medicinal plant products is controlled by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$

RESULTS

Thin layer chromatography

Bioactive compounds isolated from these medicinal plant products using mobile phase chloroform and methanol along with retention factor (Rf values) and compared with reference values (Rv) which is mentioned in the literature as shown in Table 1. Overall, the results showed some similarity related to thin layer chromatography studies.

Estimation of total cellular content

The effect of these plant fractions on total cellular content as shown in Table 2. The results of these studies claimed that these plant fractions showed enhancement in total cellular content at higher doses as compared to control. The maximum effect of these plant fractions related to antidiabetic effect at lower doses in case of *Syzygium cumini* and *Salavadora persica* as compared to Huminsulin 50/50.

Estimation of free hemoglobin content

In addition, similar results also observed in free hemoglobin in the supernatant containing plant extracts (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Thin layer chromatography of medicinal plant products.

Plant Name	Bioactive compound	Mobile phase	Rf values	Reported values	References
Fenugreek	Saponin	C:M (15:1)	0.83, 0.95, 0.59	0.62, 0.75, 0.87, 0.90, 0.95, 0.98	Sharma et al. 2013 [21]
<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Tannin	C:M (27:0.3)	0.37, 0.18, 0.13, 0.67, 0.83	0.26, 0.46, 0.66, 0.72.	Benmehdi et al. 2012 [22]
<i>Salvadora persica</i>	Flavonoid	C:M (18:2)	0.10, 0.21, 0.70, 0.97	0.18, 0.21, 0.68, 0.98	Iwashina et al. 2013 [23]
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Flavonoid	C:M (18:2)	0.94, 0.64, 0.30	0.37, 0.64	Victorio et al. 2009 [24]

C:M-chloroform: methanol.

Table 2. Effect of variable doses of fractions isolated from medicinal plant products on total cellular content.

Treatment	Doses (μg)	Total cellular content (mg/ml)	% Suppression/Stimulation
Control	-	0.278 ± 0.06	-
<i>Trigonella foenum graecum</i> (Fenugreek)	25	$0.176 \pm 0.02^{**}$	36.69 ↓
	50	0.242 ± 0.04	12.94 ↓
	100	0.322 ± 0.08	15.82 ↑
	200	0.388 ± 0.12	39.56 ↑
Control	-	0.278 ± 0.06	
<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	25	$0.108 \pm 0.02^{***}$	61.15 ↓
	50	$0.186 \pm 0.04^{**}$	33.09 ↓
	100	$0.222 \pm 0.04^*$	20.14 ↓
	200	0.314 ± 0.10	12.94 ↑
Control	-	0.278 ± 0.06	
<i>Salvadora persica</i>	25	$0.148 \pm 0.08^{**}$	46.76 ↓
	50	0.242 ± 0.10	12.94 ↓
	100	0.312 ± 0.14	12.23 ↑
	200	0.384 ± 0.12	38.12 ↑
Control	-	0.278 ± 0.06	
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	25	$0.198 \pm 0.012^*$	28.77 ↓
	50	0.284 ± 0.06	2.15 ↑
	100	0.398 ± 0.14	43.16 ↑
	200	0.476 ± 0.24	71.22 ↑
Huminsulin 50/50	10	$0.154 \pm 0.02^{**}$	44.6 ↓

Lysed diabetic human whole blood (high glucose content) were cultured with variable doses of fractions isolated from medicinal plant products. Total cellular content was measured after high speed centrifugation and collect supernatant for estimation of total cellular content. Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E. The difference between control and variable doses of medicinal plant products is controlled by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$.

Fig.1. Estimation of free hemoglobin content in the supernatant of diabetic human whole blood samples containing plant extracts. Lysed diabetic human whole blood (high glucose content) were cultured with variable doses of medicinal plant products (as described in materials and methods section). Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E. The difference between control and variable doses of medicinal plant products is controlled by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$.

Table 3. Effect of variable doses of fractions isolated from medicinal plant products on total glucose content in human diabetic blood samples.

Treatment	Doses (μg)	Total glucose content (mg/ml)	% Suppression/ Stimulation
Control	-	2.88 ± 0.16	-
<i>Trigonella foenum graecum</i> (Fenugreek)	25	$1.88 \pm 0.12^{**}$	34.72 ↓
	50	$2.12 \pm 0.08^*$	26.38 ↓
	100	2.94 ± 0.16	2.08 ↑
	200	3.48 ± 0.24	20.83 ↑
Control	-	2.88 ± 0.16	
<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	25	$1.04 \pm 0.004^{***}$	63.88 ↓
	50	$1.76 \pm 0.02^{**}$	38.88 ↓
	100	2.44 ± 0.78	15.27 ↓
	200	3.76 ± 0.68	30.55 ↑
Control	-	2.88 ± 0.16	
<i>Salvadora persica</i>	25	$1.44 \pm 0.04^{***}$	50.0 ↓
	50	$1.98 \pm 0.06^{**}$	31.25 ↓
	100	2.66 ± 0.04	7.63 ↓
	200	3.44 ± 0.18	19.44 ↑
Control	-	2.88 ± 0.16	
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	25	$2.08 \pm 0.72^{**}$	27.77 ↓
	50	3.02 ± 0.98	4.86 ↑
	100	3.76 ± 0.74	30.55 ↑
	200	4.12 ± 0.54	43.05 ↑
Huminsulin 50/50	10	$1.52 \pm 0.44^{**}$	47.22 ↓

Non infected lysed human whole blood samples were cultured for 48 h incubation along with variable doses of glucose content. Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E. The difference between control and variable doses of medicinal plant products is controlled by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test). * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$.

Overall, the results claimed that these plant extracts at lower doses showed antidiabetic effect because of decline in free hemoglobin in the supernatant. The maximum effect was observed in case of fractions isolated from *Syzygium cumini* and *Salavadora persica*. In addition, *Trigonella foenum graecum* (Fenugreek) and *Terminalia chebula* showed less anti-diabetic effect.

Estimation of glucose content

The effect of these test materials on glucose content in human whole blood samples as shown in Table 3. The results of these studies showed that these plant extracts especially *Syzygium cumini* and *Salavadora persica* showed declined in glucose content at lower doses as compared to Huminsulin 50/50.

DISCUSSION

Use of medicinal plant products for human health against various infectious diseases which is already mentioned in the literature. In other words, these medicinal plants plays a crucial role in the development of human health which is more affordable and easily accessible source of treatment. Recently there is increased interest in natural products among researchers for their utilization especially in case of prophylactic and therapeutic treatment which basically needs to isolate, purify and structurally characterize these active constituents as well as to study the biological activities of naturally occurring primary and secondary metabolites [25]. For these studies, thin layer chromatography is required to identify and separated the bioactive compounds. This technique is considered to be more versatile, inexpensive techniques

that quickly separate and isolate the biochemical compounds from mixture compounds. The method is also applicable in forensic science to identify drugs of abuse in body fluids [27]. In our study, we have applied this method to detect the biologically active phytochemicals. We have tried different concentration of the solvent system to achieve a better separation of the bioactive compounds. As shown in Table 1, our group separated bioactive compounds that are mentioned in the selected solvent systems. In our previous work, we had screened the different solvent extracts for their inhibition of alpha amylase activity [27-30]. The solvent that gave the best results (highest percent of alpha amylase inhibition) are further analyzed for their bioactive compound. Our values were well matched with the literature (Table 1) confirming that a petroleum ether extract of fenugreek contains saponins as a bioactive compound, the antidiabetic activity of *Syzygium cumini* is due to the presence of tannins while *Salvadora persica* and *Terminalia chebula* are rich in flavonoids that make them to become a better antidiabetic agent.

In this study, exposure of these fractions isolated from medicinal plant products caused a reduction in the blood glucose level and total cellular content at lower doses in case of lysed diabetic human whole blood samples. The decreased glucose level in lysed diabetic human whole blood clearly showed the anti-hyperglycaemic effect of these fractions and seem to justify the claim of the traditional healers. Further studies are needed to confirm the hypoglycemic activity of this plant and to evaluate its potential in the treatment of diabetes. According to literature there are two factors those specially are associated with diabetic profile, low hemoglobin concentration in blood as well as high blood glucose concentration in the blood [31, 32]. Regulation of these component using herbal treatment is the goal of the study. Scientific validation of these fractions isolated from medicinal plant products which has proved its efficacy in order to reducing the sugar level which is confirmed and detected through free hemoglobin content and glucose estimation in lysed human diabetic whole blood samples. From these results related to its potential effectiveness against diabetes, it is assumed that these fractions isolated from medicinal plant products that played in the management of diabetes, which needs further exploration for necessary development of drugs and nutraceuticals from natural resource.

CONCLUSION

By analyzing the result we have concluded that secondary metabolites isolated from four plants viz. *Trigonella foenum graecum* (Fenugreek), *Syzygium cumini*, *Salvadora persica* and *Terminalia chebula* possess and

showed potent antidiabetic activity. Further investigation is required to purify the exact bioactive compound which can be served as a potent antidiabetic drug.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

This work was carried out in collaboration between four authors. AG designed the study, wrote the protocol and interpreted the data where TB anchored the field study, gathered the initial data related to her PhD work under AG guidance and performed preliminary data analysis. AG, TB, BS and BKS managed the literature searches whereas AG and TB produced the initial draft. The final manuscript has been read and approved by all authors.

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